

How To realize student-centered teaching in Cloud Class

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Abstract:The student-centered teaching innovation has certain universality, from the teaching method angle it aims at the student's study and the growth demand, uses the information method to create the innovation teaching method. The innovation practice centering on the development of students can improve the students' learning experience and learning achievement. We Use the three-dimensional network problem-oriented map to stimulate students' learning motivation, and use questionnaire survey, celebrity interviews, real-life happiness model analysis to achieve the student-centered teaching practice of mixed cloud class, improve the well-being of students' life value, and create a happy teaching model.

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First, the background of teaching reform, the current higher education popularization and marketization, education and teaching to solve the two major contradictions. The contradictions are embodied in the regular classes in schools, the unified teaching materials and examinations, the class teaching system and the students' individualized development, and the diversified professional posts in the customized production of enterprises. The second contradiction is the contradiction between the huge ability demand and expectation of the graduates and the backward education system which is only guided by the tradition of the university. The modern Western "new three centers" take the student development as the teaching core, the teacher's teaching activity is serving for the student's Development and the success; take the student study as the center, arranging the study according to the brain science and the cognition rule, the teaching serves for the student, learning by means of information; learning effect emphasizes the purpose of learning rather than the form of learning. Figure 1: Three Dimensional Network model framework, excessive teaching groups in the context of learning, teaching methods need to change the role of identity; teachers must organize learning rather than teaching, what teachers should do in the classroom is of course important, but more important is what students do. Learn from the National Training Laboratory in Maine, learn pyramid's teaching method, psychologist Carroll's learning model expressed in learning time, to achieve the ideal state of teaching innovation, from learning motivation, attitude, content, method, ability to change the traditional knowledge-centered teaching method

into the Trinity Teaching method, namely, Value Molding, ability training and knowledge acquisition to achieve the goal of improving the quality of life and life value. Third, the innovative practice and exploration of teaching, the cultivation of students' ability needs training, the cultivation of value needs experience, so it is inseparable from the platform. The teaching method of mobile phone leading course in cloud class can enliven the classroom atmosphere effectively. For example, the use of mobile phone cloud class to participate in the answer to the question of the choice. It not only improves the students' sense of participation in class, but also improves the efficiency of learning. Cloud class can divide the teaching knowledge into different task points. At the same time through the cloud class we can also integrate ideological and political courses, group display discipline, littering, group collective sense of honor into the classroom to restrain student behavior. Timekeepers standing in the perspective of others to consider how the rational integration of creative countdown with different colors of the card as a minute reminder card better serve them, which embodies the connotation of innovation. Such as group cooperation ability, communication ability, mind guide group method, poster learning method, key words card, placeholder method, guessing method, debate and so on. Short answers should not be copied and pasted by students, but should be presented in an appropriate way, such as group or individual using mind maps or fish bone diagrams, group debate on behalf of representatives, through the cloud class election, a variety of creative and interesting cloud class tools are used to complete the course teaching. The production function reflects the relationship between knowledge input factors and ability output in students' learning. The utility is a mathematical expression that uses a C-D production function to calculate a production function to describe a certain combination of production factors in the production process and the dependence between its possible maximum output, A, B, C, D, E, F are the corresponding five indicators. The degree of students' preference for "self-consciousness" is reflected in the following parameters: $a = 0.5$ $b = 0.3$ $c = 0.05$

$d = 0.1$ $e = 0.05$. The happiness index is $4.145100\% = 82.8\%$, which gives the college student an academic happiness index of 82.8%. Therefore, it is further demonstrated that the learning-centered teaching method improves students' satisfaction. Figure 2: Data Analysis Framework, teachers teaching is lack of their own perception of the practice. It is not enough just to complete the routine teaching tasks and teaching materials. How to achieve the true student-centered teaching and combine the innovative means of information to enhance students' classroom experience is the only way for teachers to improve teaching methods.